

Hierarchical Clustering on Graph Embeddings: A Scalable Approach to Risky Intersections

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Introduction

- Road crashes claim **1.3 million lives annually**, the leading cause of death for those **under 29** and among the top 10 globally.
- IVORY framework.
 - [European Union's Horizon Europe](#) research and innovation programme Marie Skłodowska-Curie Industrial Doctorates (grant No 101119590).
 - It develops fair and explainable **Artificial Intelligence (AI)** to analyze driver behavior, predict crashes, and enhance road safety while sharing knowledge.
 - DC9 focuses on creating an AI framework to analyze **road safety KPIs**, predicts crashes, and evaluates the **scalability of models** primarily across spatial.
- Traditional crash prediction relies on econometrics; now enhanced by **Machine Learning (ML)** & **Deep Learning (DL)**, with **Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)** extend DL to graph-structured data.

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Data Sources

➤ OSeven Telematics provided **telematics data** collected via smartphone hardware sensors, anonymized and compliant with Greek and European personal **data protection** regulations (GDPR).

- Raw data are processed by **proprietary machine learning** algorithms.
- Reliability is validated against OBD data, on-road tests, simulators, and literature benchmarks.
- Selected **features** from the provided **preprocessed dataset**: geographic coordinates, smoothed speed, and binary flags for hazardous behaviors.

➤ OpenStreetMap is a free, editable **global map** created by volunteers and released under an open-content license.

OpenStreetMap

Telematics Aggregation

- Based on the telematics data, a coordinate **bounding box** was defined and used to extract a structured **graph** from OpenStreetMap via the **OSMnx** Python library.
- From the graph, **node** and **edge** features were stored in two different datasets.
- Telematics features were aggregated to OSM nodes using summation or averaging within a **50-meter buffer**, coherently with existing literature.
- Each raw telematics point was matched to its **closest edge**, and features were aggregated per edge.

Features	Description
Street_Count	Number of streets connected to the intersection
SmoothenedSpeed	Average speed of vehicles near the node
SpeedingFlag	Count of speeding events near the node
Mobile_usage	Number of instances of phone usage near the node
Harsh_acc	Number of harsh acceleration events near the node
Harsh_brk	Number of harsh braking events near the node
Event_intensity	Average intensity of harsh events near the node
Trips_count	Number of trips recorded near the node

Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering

- Clustering is an unsupervised machine learning technique to group **similar items**.
- An **Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering** is an approach aiming to find a hierarchy of data point groups.
 - The method builds on a criterion to determine the distance between clusters, called **Linkage Method**, which has an impact on the shape and size of the clusters.
 - The **Cophenetic Correlation Coefficient (CCC)** is used to assess the clustering performance, defining how well the algorithm preserves the pairwise distances of the original data points.

- The output is a **dendrogram** displaying the hierarchical relationship between different sets of data.

Introduction to GNNs

- GNNs learn compact **vector representations** of nodes that capture structural roles, **neighborhood context**, and node features.
- They encode graph-structured data by leveraging **topological relationships** rather than flattening the graph into vectors.
- Advancements include **Graph Convolutional Networks** (GCN) using convolution operations, and **Graph Attention Networks** (GAT) applying **attention mechanisms**.
- A simple neural network with two GAT layers was defined.
 - Leveraging **attention coefficients** to weigh neighbors differently and to incorporate both **edge features** and **neighboring nodes**.
 - Using a **multi-head attention** to stabilize training and improve accuracy.
 - Trained within a self-supervised framework, using a self-designed **contrastive loss function** inspired by literature in this field.

Dendrogram Analysis of Raw Features

- A **dendrogram** displays the step-by-step grouping of data points, where the **height** of each merge shows how far apart clusters are when they merge.
 - At each merge, if the **linkage height \leq threshold**, the clusters are colored the same.
 - In SciPy, the default color threshold is **70% of the maximum merge height**.
 - If most of the dendrogram is **one color**, the data forms one large cluster with a few smaller or outlier groups standing apart at that level.
- **Ward's** method achieves a **moderate CCC** and more clearly **separates** dense data points.
 - While it sacrifices **exact pairwise distances** to form clusters, different stem lengths in the dendrogram still show **meaningful separation**.

Linkage	CCC
Ward	0.616
Single	0.652
Complete	0.682
Average	0.931
Centroid	0.916
Median	0.499

Dendrogram Analysis of Embeddings

- Most dendrograms show **one color**, meaning the data forms a single large, **dense** cluster at **low linkage heights**.
 - The single method exhibits an emphasized **chaining effect**, indicating a **continuous structure** in the data, expected from the embedding process, further highlighted by high CCC.
- **Ward's** method achieves a **good CCC** and produces clearer cluster separation.
 - One large cluster with two smaller groups emerge.
- The Ward's method using embeddings (instead of raw features) achieved a **higher CCC**.
 - For analysis, cluster labels were **mapped back** to the raw features and **averaged**.

Linkage	CCC
Ward	0.690
Single	0.792
Complete	0.746
Average	0.930
Centroid	0.925
Median	0.553

Discussion: Key Insights (1/2)

- The dendrogram encourages separation in **2 clusters**:
 - One **risky cluster** displaying increased speeding events, mobile usage, and more frequent harsh events and trips.
 - The other displays **lower-risk traits**, though with a **comparable average speed**.

Features	Cluster 1 Mean Values (31,409 nodes)	Cluster 2 Mean Values (467 nodes)
Street_Count	3.36	3.24
SmoothenedSpeed	27.08	31.26
SpeedingFlag	4.59	34.92
Mobile_usage	10.59	99.19
Harsh_acc	0.36	4.16
Harsh_brk	0.31	3.36
Event_intensity	0.37	1.37
Trips_count	25.53	230.16

Discussion: Key Insights (2/2)

- Downwards, the number of clusters **increased to 3**, resulting in the previous safer cluster being split into two subgroups:
 - These **new clusters** show similar levels of harsh events and mobile usage, both lower than the original risky cluster.
 - However, the **smaller of the two** has the highest average speed, making it risky in terms of speed, while the **original risky** cluster remains higher in harsh events and phone use.

Features	Cluster 1 Mean Values (29,937 nodes)	Cluster 2 Mean Values (1,472 nodes)	Cluster 3 Mean Values (467 nodes)
Street_Count	3.37	3.19	3.24
SmoothenedSpeed	25.99	49.33	31.26
SpeedingFlag	3.07	35.31	34.92
Mobile_usage	10.62	10.02	99.19
Harsh_acc	0.36	0.47	4.16
Harsh_brk	0.30	0.56	3.36
Event_intensity	0.36	0.62	1.37
Trips_count	24.55	45.5	230.16

Potential applications

➤ The work aims to provide node-based insights, informing on where to focus safety efforts and resources to improve overall **traffic road safety**.

- Risky cluster areas can be targeted for interventions to enhance road safety, such as **infrastructure improvements**, awareness **campaigns**, or **enforcement measures**.
- Insurers can use this clustering to define **risk profiles** by identifying patterns of risky or safe driving behavior, enabling insurers to offer more accurate, **location-based pricing** and **targeted advice**.
- The hierarchical structure enables **finer granularity** for more targeted interventions. Lower in the hierarchy, clusters may reflect **different risk types**, such as speed-related or harsh event and phone-related behavior.

Conclusions

- Graph-based **representations** improve the understanding of complex road safety data by leveraging node features, topology, and edge attributes to enhance **clustering performance**.
- The resulting hierarchy enables clearer cluster selection via dendrograms and supports **scalable analysis** for deeper road safety insights. Dividing the safer cluster reveals **alternative risk perspectives**, highlighting the value of multi-level clustering for **capturing nuanced behaviors**.
- Future directions may include testing **different GNN architectures** and **linkage methods**.
- Incorporating **traffic, temporal, and contextual features**, such as rural vs. urban classification, could enhance real-world relevance.
- However, hierarchical clustering remains **computationally intensive**, requiring significant resources, particularly with large-scale graphs.

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